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Manual: image integration in cBioPortal

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Introduction

The integration of radiological and histopathological whole slide images (WSI) in cBioPortal was demonstrated in milestone 6¹ of EOSC4Cancer. This document describes the required steps to realise image integration in cBioPortal.

Methods

The minimal requirements are that cBioPortal is deployed² and there is a study with data loaded³. For the image integration, we used the ability of cBioPortal to include other types of data through resource data⁴. The linkage of an image viewer essentially entails adding resource data, including a URL to an image viewer, to the sample resource data file⁵ or patient resource data file⁶ in a cBioPortal study. The images can then be viewed in an embedded tab on the cBioPortal Patient View via iframe. This process is very flexible and we provide a description for two particular examples, i.e. XNAT for radiological images (see Figure 1) and xOpat for WSI (see Figure 2). Note that with different use cases, the deployment process might be different.

Figure 1. Screenshot of radiology image integration through XNAT

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https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1AibOFjJ2s3hZrul86dixHy8KGkT_NwPW/edit?usp=drive_link&ouid=101996802771845133093&rtpof=true&sd=true

2 <https://docs.cbioportal.org/deployment/docker/>

3 <https://docs.cbioportal.org/study-curation-guide/>

4 <https://docs.cbioportal.org/file-formats/#resource-data>

5 <https://docs.cbioportal.org/file-formats/#example-sample-resource-data-file>

6 <https://docs.cbioportal.org/file-formats/#example-patient-resource-data-file>

Figure 2. Screenshot of WSI integration through xOpat

XNAT resource data generation

XNAT⁷, the extensible neuroimaging archive toolkit, is an open-source solution designed for sharing and storing medical imaging data, especially radiology data, in DICOM format. In this example, a patient resource data file was generated for the radiological images in an XNAT project to be visualised in cBioPortal. To generate this patient resource data file, the **xnat2cbio**⁸ tool was developed within EOESC4Cancer. This tool first queries projects on XNAT and extracts the required information at patient level. Next, the resource data is formatted to match the format required by cBioPortal. An example of the patient resource data file generated by the xnat2cbio tool, which includes a URL to an XNAT integrated OHIF viewer can be found in the same GitHub project⁹.

xOpat resource data generation

xOpat¹⁰, eXplainable Open Pathology Analysis Tool, is an open-source whole slide image viewer. In this example, a sample resource data file was generated for WSI to be visualised in cBioPortal. The metadata of these WSI were obtained from different sources (e.g. Microsoft Excel sheet for anonymized data or OpenEHR database for the CRC Cohort) and therefore instead of implementing multiple direct tools for importing, we started from generic CSV files. To generate the sample resource data file, the **csv2cbio**¹¹ tool was developed within EOESC4Cancer.

To generate the URL to the *WSI Server* that delivers the actual WSI data, we also had to construct a CSV file, with the following syntax

<first namespace group> <second namespace group> <type-id> <case-id> <path>

⁷ <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1385/NI:5:1:11>

⁸ <https://gitlab.com/radiology/infrastructure/utills/xnat2cbio>

⁹ https://gitlab.com/radiology/infrastructure/utills/xnat2cbio/-/blob/main/example_output/xnat-cbio.txt?ref_type=heads

¹⁰ <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/cgf.14812>

¹¹ <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/csv2cbio>

The final <ID> is constructed as **mmci.anon.w.S273-7** slide, which belongs to a **mmci.anon.c.P273**¹² case (see example below).

```
mmci anon S273-7 P273 /mmci/anon/P273-S273-7.mrxs
```

```
mmci anon S273-6 P273 /mmci/anon/P273-S273-6.mrxs
```

Here, we use the data institution origin and project name as the groups. These IDs can then be easily used for authorization logic. The default order of columns can be changed by environment variables. The viewer then uses these IDs to access given slides.

Besides being able to consume arbitrary CSV data, the csv2cbio tool also includes logics for automatic study import & deletion.

Authentication and authorisation

The authentication and authorisation for access to the image data through the viewers integrated in cBioPortal is not employed on cBioPortal itself. Rather it is arranged by XNAT for radiological images and xOpat for WSI as the image data is deposited there.

Life Science (LS) AAI

Authentication was arranged via LS AAI – OpenID Connect provider – to manage OAuth2 clients for xOpat. Keycloak could be an alternative if you prefer a locally managed provider. Authentication is not supported with default CbioPortal importing procedure, as the validation scripts provided do not account for authentication tokens, these tokens are injected by csv2cbio. Similar to how data detection mappers are injectable, the Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting (AAA) logics can also be injected by implementing a given interface and configuring environmental variables properly. In this case the built-in authentication-only logic based on JSON Web Token (JWT) tokens by Empaia was used. Built-in logic for authentication is no-auth, disabled-access (the default) and JWT authentication. The authentication is implemented such that a FastAPI method is injected in each API call and the auth script defines what the injection validates – be it a JWT or anything else. To authorise, you have to implement your custom logic in the interface hooks. These functions receive anything that the injected method has provided (e.g. a parsed and validated JWT token), and the ID of the particular entity that is being queried.

For a more detailed explanation of the authentication and authorisation implementation, please see [Appendix II: authentication & authorization modifications to cBioPortal](#).

Discussion and ongoing developments

Not all functionality was tested during the demonstrator. There are a couple of developments ongoing that will be described in more detail in an updated version of this manual.

Authentication sharing between cBioPortal and xOpat

Our logics is based on the following pull requests on the cBioPortal: to modularize the custom oauth2 process: separate two models when accessing the database (the fetch-study-group model and the get/write user+authorities model), and enables custom implementation of SecurityRepository interface so that database access can be replaced with e.g. parsing user information from the OIDC provider¹³. Additionally, a suggestion was made to replace the jwt parsing from spring with a jwt parsing from the jwt.io recommended library¹⁴.

¹² Types include: **w** = wsi, a slide object, **c** = case, a case object

¹³ <https://github.com/cBioPortal/cbioportal/pull/11053>

¹⁴ <https://github.com/cBioPortal/cbioportal/pull/11063>

Using these modifications, with v6 cBioPortal is able to connect to a custom OIDC provider. We solve authorization by implementing custom resolvers on both WSI Service and cBioPortal. cBioPortal is able to dynamically construct study groups (=authorities) the user has access to based on the user metadata from LSAAI. Similarly, WSI Service can dynamically resolve which slides the user can view. Users are then assigned to groups in LSAAI manager Perun, and groups are translated to either study authorities, or matched against slide IDs.

Authentication in XNAT

For the demonstrator a public XNAT project was used, which does not require authentication. When a non-public XNAT project is integrated in cBioPortal, the default authentication of XNAT will be used and the user will be asked to login (by using the already granted credentials for that XNAT instance) before images can be viewed.

Resource data extracted from XNAT

Currently the xnat2cbio tool provides resource data at patient level. In practice this means that the URL to the OHIF viewer points to all images of a patient and not a specific image or timepoint. Nevertheless, it is possible to modify the URL to point to a specific scan session or image.

The IDs extracted from XNAT are not guaranteed to match with the patient or sample ID used in cBioPortal. The user will therefore have to check the file created by xnat2cbio to verify the XNAT ID matches the cBioPortal ID.

Conclusion

XNAT integration

The xnat2cbio tool was developed to generate resource data, including a URL to an OHIF viewer. Through this URL, integration of the OHIF viewer allows for visualisation of radiological images in cBioPortal.

xOpat integration

The csv2cbio tool was developed to generate resource data to a WSI viewer for integration in cBioPortal. The URL in the generated resource data allows for visualisation of WSI in cBioPortal.